

Manufacturing Changeability and Manufacturing as a Service

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Abstract: As markets and supply chains become more volatile, rapid response to changing demands is crucial. Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) enables quick access to manufacturing assets, while changeable manufacturing designs adaptable systems. This paper investigates how 1) manufacturing as a service may support changeability, and 2) how changeability may support manufacturing as a service. To do so, a representative literature review on the bidirectional support of changeability and manufacturing as a service is conducted. Consequently, the means changeability provides to enable and/or stimulate manufacturing as a service are studied. Additionally, how manufacturing as a service can support changeability in different levels of a production system is discussed. Findings show MaaS fosters manufacturing flexibility, while changeability strengthens MaaS in three areas: strategy (market adaptability), technology (flexible systems), and organization (operational agility). Together, they enhance manufacturing resilience and responsiveness.

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Keywords: Manufacturing as a Service, Changeability, Servitisation, Production Systems, Flexibility.

INTRODUCTION

As the rate of global consumption is increasing, the demand for products and services is elevating in the international marketplace. To that point, alternate and more responsible models of consumption and production respond to the awareness about the negative impacts of overconsumption on society and the environment (Hunka et al., 2020). Consequently, collaborative consumption and sharing of resources have become popular among diverse groups and the sharing economy is replacing traditional business models in different sectors. Albinsson & Yasanthi (Albinsson & Yasanthi Perera, 2012) defined the Sharing Economy as “a-to-peer-based activity of obtaining, giving, or sharing the access to goods and services, coordinated through community-based online services”. In the manufacturing sector, this trend and the servitisation trend led to the introduction of Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS). Corti et al. (Corti et al., 2021) describes MaaS as a part of the “sharing economy” trend and identifies it as “having access to third-party machinery to increase the saturation of the machines in times that the system is facing low productivity”. They also mention that since MaaS allows the sharing of resources, it indeed reactivates the added value of the machinery which is left unused.

As an effort to establish a class of manufacturing systems that would be as efficient as dedicated manufacturing systems, while providing the same benefits in terms of flexibility as flexible manufacturing systems, Koren et al. in 1999 (Koren, 2019) introduced the concept of reconfigurable manufacturing systems. Reconfigurable manufacturing systems are systems that are modular, and by design prepared for changing capacity or functionality rapidly on demand (Koren, 2019). While the concept of reconfigurable manufacturing systems addresses a very specific context, the manufacturing system, and a specific type and scope of change, Wiendahl et al. (Wiendahl et al., 2007) suggested the broader concept of manufacturing changeability, which includes not only reconfigurability, but also changeability on other levels. Changeable manufacturing aims at establishing manufacturing systems that can respond efficiently to changes in the products, processes, volume and mix, influenced by change drivers such as volatility, variety or strategy by applying various change enablers (H. ElMaraghy & Wiendahl, 2016). The aim of this paper is to explore the relationship between the two concepts of manufacturing as a service and changeable manufacturing. To achieve this, section 2 defines the two concepts. Section 3 presents the research question, then section 4 stresses the identified relationships.

DEFINITIONS OF CONCEPTS

2.1. Manufacturing as a Service

Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) first appeared in the literature in the 90s (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990a) as a new flexible sourcing method. The service offers ranges from the design of the product, customization of the product design, flexible contractual relationship, to efficient information transaction between customer and provider. MaaS promises rapid response time accompanied by opportunities for flexibility and consequently competitiveness for the enterprises. In this context, a company offers unused manufacturing capacity to a business customer.

Gong et al (Gong et al., 2023) refers to MaaS as a promising means of open business operations as it leaves the boundaries in the organization to distribute resources and capabilities among the shared stakeholders. Additionally, they differentiate MaaS with conventional outsourcing strategy: outsourcing delegates a task to a selected agent while MaaS benefits from a crowdsourcing model to open a call to a crowd to exploit efficiently the external resources. Tedaldi & Miragliotta (Tedaldi & Miragliotta, 2023) relate MaaS to the servitisation trend in manufacturing systems where organizations look for competitiveness through adding services to their conventional offerings. They characterize servitisation by Product-Service System (PSS), where "sale of use" matters more than "sale of product". Therefore, PSS is a combination of "servitisation of products" and "productization of services". On the contrary, MaaS focuses on the relationship between supplier-customer rather than product-service. Bulut et al. (Bulut et al., 2021) associates MaaS with the Everything-as-a-Service (XaaS) paradigm, where the customer has access to all resources as a service through a cloud. They place MaaS in this paradigm alongside Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS), Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) and Infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) and define it as the provision of physical manufacturing resources and capabilities to the customers so that customers can use them based on their existing manufacturing requirements.

2.2. Changeability

Wiendahl et al. (Wiendahl et al., 2007) defined changeable manufacturing as "the ability of a manufacturing system to economically accomplish early and foresighted adjustments of the factory's structures and processes on all levels in response to change impulses". They proposed a classification of changeability, consisting of five distinct classes, each corresponding to different production levels on one side and product levels on the other side:

1) Changeover Ability: The operational capacity of a single machine to perform designated tasks on a known workpiece readily with minimal downtime. **2) Flexibility:** The operational capacity of a system to adapt within a predefined product family through adjustments like reprogramming and rerouting. **3) Reconfigurability:** The tactical ability of a production area to switch to similar products within a predefined group through physical changes to processes and material flow. **4) Transformability:** The tactical ability of an entire factory to adapt to different product groups, requiring structural interventions across production, logistics, facilities, and personnel. **5) Agility:** The strategic ability of a company to respond to market shifts by pursuing new markets, developing products and services, and building necessary production capacity.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The two concepts of MaaS and manufacturing changeability are similar concepts in terms of both focusing on supporting a more dynamic and more volatile manufacturing environment. They both generally aim at providing a more agile approach to manufacturing to faster respond to changes in demand in terms of volume and product variety. However, whereas the literature traditionally frames MaaS as a new business model opportunity for inter-organizational collaboration, manufacturing changeability has focused more on how to develop and structure a manufacturing system with little focus on external delivery of services. The two concepts share the same general aim but there is no existing literature regarding interrelations between them, this paper therefore, explores the relations, leading to the following two research questions: **RQ1:** How does the concept of changeability support manufacturing as a service? **RQ2:** How does the concept of manufacturing as a service support or enable changeability?

FINDINGS

To answer the two RQs, this article presents two separate approaches. The first approach, detailed in 4.1, leans toward the support that changeability brings for MaaS. In 4.2, the second approach investigates MaaS support for different classes of changeability. Each section describes in detail the respected approach.

4.1. Changeability supporting MaaS

Goldhar & Jelinek (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990a) pointed out the challenge of this paradigm: "The easiest [changes] are in the technology. Much more difficult are the necessary changes in strategy, organization, accounting and financial analysis and operations management. [...] The real barriers we face are cultural, organizational, and strategic." To

answer the first RQ, we use this typology to present the strategic, technological and organizational enablers of MaaS. The cultural barriers are outside our scope. We also use the same typology (strategic, technologic and organizational categories) to investigate the incentives of MaaS. To do so, a literature review was conducted to extract enablers and incentives of MaaS. The literature review methodology is shown in Figure 1, however, it is representative and does not present a systematic review as methodology.

Figure 1. Research methodology for RQ1

Furthermore, this study addresses the five classes of changeability (namely: changeover ability (Class I), flexibility (Class II), reconfigurability (Class III), transformability (class IV) and agility (Class V)) to see which will provide the means for each of MaaS enablers and incentives (see

Table 1 and Table 2). In the following, we will discuss the discovered support the classes of changeability bring for MaaS in three aspects of strategy, technology and organizational.

Strategy

Changeability supports MaaS through two strategies: generic and MaaS-dedicated. According to (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990a), systems prioritizing precision over flexibility profit from long-run production of standardized products. However, as markets saturate, decision-makers must balance capital investment and innovation. High interest rates and limited capital discourage innovation, leading to outdated production systems resistant to change. Attempts to optimize these rigid systems only extend production cycles for return of investment (ROI).

New manufacturing technology shifts the economy from scale to scope, enabling product variety at the same cost as standardization. Continuous innovation ensures productivity and competitiveness in the global market. Businesses that embrace change prioritize skilled teams with autonomy, focusing on flexibility, customization, and innovation. These principles shape new business models, with efficient and rapid creation of local value networks and the connection to for innovative providers, facilitating their process of resource, service, and value sharing (Corti et al., 2021). Network intermediaries match customer needs with expert providers, enabling tailored manufacturing processes (Bulut et al., 2021).

(Zolnowski et al., 2014) emphasize transitioning from product to service, production to use, transaction to relationship and supply chain to value networks. To remain competitive, organizations must adapt their values, key propositions, pricing, and resources in an agile manner, aligning with partners (Chaudhuri et al., 2021; Hasan et al., 2007; Zolnowski et al., 2014).

Technology

Changeability can technologically support MaaS in two areas: Manufacturing and External/Internal IT support.

As for the manufacturing area, (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990a) state that an effective manufacturing system requires maximum flexibility and quick turnaround capability for new product ramps. This flexibility enables incremental technological changes and shifts the focus from "trade-offs" to cohesive strategies that combine R&D, engineering, marketing, and manufacturing into an integrated product delivery system. Increased adaptability and rapid changeover capability, enabled by cross-functional integration, expands market opportunities without disrupting existing relationships. These technological shifts, paired with strategic resource allocation, improve certainty, predictability, and control in manufacturing, while enhancing quality, variety, and capacity to innovate (Gawer & Cusumano, 2013; Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b). Consequently, a combination of flexibility, responsiveness to change, predictability, and accuracy will be more effective for economies of scope than scale which leads to a more competitive edge. Tedaldi and Miragliotta (Miragliotta et al., 2022; Tedaldi & Miragliotta, 2021) highlight Cloud Manufacturing (CM) as a key enabler of flexible sourcing, allowing providers to offer customized products with variable delivery dates, volumes, and mixes. CM accelerates response times and fosters adaptive contractual relationships, paving the way for service-oriented manufacturing and supply chains.

Regarding IT support, Adamson et al. (Adamson et al., 2017) noted that development of technologies of CM, brings positive effect: agility and rapid respond to the changing demand of customer, capability to leverage different combination of products and service, flexibility to up- and downscaling and ease of information sharing internally and externally through platforms. Cloud technologies facilitate collaboration within manufacturing systems and with customers, allowing real-time value exchange and adaptive responses to market shifts. These capabilities promote resource-sharing models such as MaaS (Manufacturing as a Service), DaaS (Design-as-a-Service), and MCaaS (Machining-as-a-Service). (Tedaldi & Miragliotta, 2021) further explain that manufacturing grids enable companies to collaborate through coordinated sharing, integration, and interoperability of distributed resources, supported by advanced IT and management techniques. This creates a more flexible customer-supplier relationship, reinforcing the service-oriented manufacturing model. (Kusiak, 2020) suggests that MaaS providers drive two types of innovation: technological, through material and process advancements, and organizational, through interactions with customers. Agility and flexibility enhance resource management, while reconfigurability and transformability facilitate process innovation, making MaaS a key driver of industrial evolution.

Organizational

Changeability can organizationally support MaaS in two areas: Manufacturing and Internal support.

Regarding Manufacturing, (Jafarnejad Ghomi et al., 2019) highlight that cloud manufacturing technologies enable real-time service load monitoring and balancing, enhancing transparency and managerial flexibility in decision-making. . This helps organizations have more flexibility in scheduling and service composition as well as more cohesion among the internal entities and providers, enabling the organization to provide manufacturing and resources as a service offering on-demand manufacturing service to the users.

non-deniable factor in resource and service sharing, especially in MaaS platforms. Implementing MaaS should permit to deploy a structured and homogenous system with access to information and multiple harmonized

perspectives that add up to operation and tactical ability of the manufacturing system and facilitates utilization of capacity and resources (Albinsson & Yasanthi Perera, 2012).

4.2. MaaS supporting Changeability

According to the CIRP Encyclopaedia of Production Engineering, Changeable manufacturing, and accordingly changeability, is defined as “the ability of a manufacturing system to economically accomplish early and foresighted adjustments of the factory’s structures and processes on all levels in response to change impulses”.

Wiendahl et al. (Wiendahl et al., 2007) classify changeability into five distinct classes representing different levels in the production perspective as well as the product perspective. The impact of applying MaaS in terms of supporting changeability will depend on the targeted class of changeability. Table 1 summarizes how MaaS may impact changeability on different levels. Rather than adhering to the original definition of the changeability classes from (Wiendahl et al., 2007), we extend the definition to address changeability across organizations and companies, as suggested by Mikusz et al. (Mikusz et al., 2016).

Changeover Ability

The changeover ability is the ability to do efficient changeovers on station level within existing or previously known part variants. MaaS could support change over ability by being inherently data-driven. As manufacturing assets become more digitized over time, more changeover effort is needed in terms of reprogramming machines and tools. One central element in MaaS is to enable fast connections between service providers and service consumers, facilitating

Table 1. Changeability fostering MaaS enablers

Changeability Class					Strategy	Changeability Class					Technology	Changeability Class					Organizational
I	II	III	IV	V		I	II	III	IV	V		I	II	III	IV	V	
X	X	X	X	X	Generic: Decision making process (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b)	X	X	X	X	X	Manufacturing: Rapid change over and ramp-up (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b)			X	X	X	Manufacturing: Costing monitoring (Chaudhuri et al., 2021)
			X	X	Dedicated MAAS: Communicate needs (Corti et al., 2021)			X	X	X	Internal IT: integration of resource and IT systems (Tedaldi & Miragliotta, 2023)	X	X				Manufacturing: Load monitoring (Jafarnejad Ghomi et al., 2019)
				X	Dedicated MAAS: - Clear commitment (Hasan et al., 2007) - Adapted business model (Zolnowski et al., 2014) - Pricing policy (Chaudhuri et al., 2021)			X	X	X	Manufacturing: Identification of capabilities (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b)						Manufacturing: Rapid quoting (Adamson et al., 2017)
											External IT / cloud Manufacturing: - Exchange with customer/ pre contract (Adamson et al., 2017) - Reliable/standard platform to provide and develop service /post contract (Corti et al., 2021) - Protect valuable information, data and know-how (Corti et al., 2021)						External Support: - Contractual service/negotiation (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b) - Relationship establishment and management (Corti et al., 2021)

Table 2. Changeability fostering MAAS incentives

Changeability Class					Strategy	Changeability Class					Technology	Changeability Class					Organizational
I	II	III	IV	V		I	II	III	IV	V		I	II	III	IV	V	
		X	X	X	Generic: - New customer segment (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b) - New potential customers (Corti et al., 2021)			X	X		Manufacturing: Competitive edge (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b)	X	X				Manufacturing: Load monitoring (Jafarnejad Ghomi et al., 2019)
X	X	X	X	X	Generic: Increase of revenue (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b)	X	X	X	X	X	Manufacturing: New capabilities (Goldhar & Jelinek, 1990b)	X	X	X	X		Internal Support: Process innovation (H. A. ElMaraghy & Wiendahl, 2009)
		X	X	X	Generic: Access to needs and ideas to be transformed in marketable innovation (Corti et al., 2021)		X				Manufacturing: Flexibility (Tedaldi & Miragliotta, 2021)			X	X	X	Internal Support: Access to structured, homogeneous and reliable information internal (Corti et al., 2021)
X	X	X	X	X	Dedicated MAAS: Value communication (Adamson et al., 2017)	X	X				Manufacturing: Load monitoring (Jafarnejad Ghomi et al., 2019)						
X	X	X	X	X	Dedicated MAAS: Make profit out of asset investment (Corti et al., 2021)						External IT: Access to structured, homogeneous and reliable information with outside (Corti et al., 2021)						
					Dedicated MAAS: Economic and resource globalization (Tedaldi & Miragliotta, 2023)												
					Dedicated MAAS: Identify opportunities for their associates (Corti et al., 2021)												

automated data transfer, including manufacturing instructions and parameters. MaaS provides infrastructure for doing this in a more uniform way and supports process automation. Thus, there is a potential that changeovers can be more efficient: faster in terms of reduced downtime with reduced worker effort needed to perform the changeover.

Flexibility

Flexibility describes the ability to adapt a production system to a different product by either reprogramming or rerouting the production flow. As reprogramming is fundamentally a changeover at station level, this implies that the mechanisms of MaaS supporting changeover ability as outlined above do also apply to flexibility and will thus support this in the same way. However, flexibility differs from changeover ability in terms of also involving rerouting, i.e. orchestrating or reorchestrating a value chain for manufacturing a product. Because of the short time span of coupling, the technology implementing MaaS includes providing a service catalogue that describes production capabilities and capacities for existing assets, as well as mechanisms for easily connecting to and operating these manufacturing services. If implemented internally in a company, and individual manufacturing processes are provided as services, this would enable doing automated routing of products through the production, by enabling the automated identification of what routes to follow and activate the services.

Reconfigurability

Reconfigurability refers to the ability of a production to change product variety, e.g., introducing new products requiring new capabilities, or changing the production capacity. The MaaS concept may support reconfigurations, since they imply adding removing or replacing modules, such as tools, machines, or stations, in a manufacturing system,

As implementing MaaS implies establishing a service catalogue, this would provide a repository of a company's manufacturing assets describing their capabilities. This would imply that companies could more easily identify if a reconfiguration is in fact necessary, or if the current flexibility allows for manufacturing the changed product without reconfiguring. Further, it implies that if a reconfiguration were necessary, the company would be able to identify more rapidly interesting existing assets from other manufacturing systems. The reconfiguration will then encompass moving one module from one system to another. Finally, as MaaS implies introducing faster connectivity, and improved integrability of manufacturing services when orchestrating value chains, the technology supporting MaaS should also reduce the time and effort needed to integrate new modules into existing production lines or value chains.

Table 3. Summary of the impact of MaaS on changeability and the relationship to organizations

Changeability Class	Impact	Organization
Agility	Impact for transformability applies; Better identification of services across factories within company; better identification and integration with suppliers.	Interorganizational
Transformability	Impact for reconfigurability applies; Better identification of existing assets for reuse; faster integration of new production lines.	Intra-or interorganizational
Reconfigurability	Impact for flexibility applies; Better and faster identification of existing assets to use in reconfigurations; faster integration of new services in existing systems.	Intraorganizational
Flexibility	Impact for changeover ability applies; Faster identification of rerouting options; Faster rerouting	Intraorganizational
Changeover ability	Data driven changeovers, increase automation and quality	Intraorganizational

Transformability

Transformability refers to the ability to make larger changes than reconfigurations, i.e., modifying an entire factory to introduce new families or types of products. This implies not reusing existing lines implementing changes, but rather establishing new production lines. Making such extensive changes to a factory would imply evaluating sourcing decisions, and determining whether parts should be manufactured internally, or procured or sourced through manufacturing service providers. In this context, MaaS supports transformability by allowing companies to more easily identify and evaluate manufacturing service providers for integrating them into their value chains. Furthermore, the mechanism outlined above, allowing to identify existing assets would also be relevant in the cases, where a factory is transformed from making a previous product, where some tools, machines, or stations may be reused. In this case, the service catalogue, and related production capabilities would support the process of identifying reusable assets.

Agility

Whereas the lower changeability classes refer to value chains mainly within a factory, agility refers to the ability to make changes in manufacturing networks. Since MaaS promotes cross organizational sharing of manufacturing capabilities and capacity, MaaS clearly supports agility. Implemented in a network of factories within a company, MaaS supports orchestrating and reorchestrating supply chains, allowing for minimizing transport and utilizing capacity globally. This also

applies to collaboration between organizations, applying MaaS in a traditional sense where service providers and service consumers would correspond to business-to-business suppliers and customers respectively. When transforming a network to change capacity or variety, this involves connecting factories in different ways. The concepts and technologies of MaaS allow for doing this more easily, for the same reasons as outlined above, i.e. faster identification and evaluation of service providers, faster integration and more efficient operations of networks of factories within or across companies.

DISCUSSION

Two different studies were conducted to investigate the support changeability and MaaS bring for each other. As the first step, we studied the means changeability can provide to enable and/or stimulate MaaS. In this study, the customer perspective was not detailed, since taking advantage of Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) as a customer could be a way to solve the innovation/productivity paradigm while avoiding investing in changeability. On the other

hand, there are factors that would enable and stimulate MaaS service providers to adopt this new paradigm. To that point, we first categorized different enablers, and incentives identified in the literature for MaaS and then studied the means each class of changeability can provide for these enablers and incentives. As scrutinized in 4.1, we found out that the 5 classes of changeability, namely changeover ability (Class I), flexibility (Class II), reconfigurability (Class III), transformability (class IV) and agility (Class V) are largely promoting MaaS. However, the concept of changeability is limited to the organization itself and will not include the customer or other associates as collaborators. Therefore, none of the classes of changeability were found competent to empower MaaS in external supports or collaborations (empty cells in

Table 1 and Table 2). Due to the restrictions found while investigating the first RQ, we needed to extend the definition for each class of changeability to cover external support and intraorganizational activities. Therefore, for the second RQ, in which we evaluated the support MaaS can bring for changeability, the extended definitions as in Table 3 were applied for the classes of changeability. Consequently, the impacts MaaS can have in each class of changeability were studied and detailed in section 4.2. Summarizing the findings, it can be noted that Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) can support changeability in all its five classes.

Looking through all the discussions above, we conclude that both concepts of MaaS and changeability are supporting each other in different classes with different factors (see Figure 1). Additionally, MaaS and changeability show support for manufacturing shift to be more dynamic and collaborative, which will help stakeholders deal with the rapidly increasing demand of the global market while trying to avoid overconsumption of resources. Collaborative consumption and resource sharing while embracing change will decrease the negative environmental and societal impacts. Additionally, they enable organizations to satisfy the changing demand of the global market with the minimum waste in a reasonable time. Altogether, the two concepts help organizations move toward more sustainability on the competitive edge.

CONCLUSIONS

Through a discussion over the literature, two RQs were addressed: RQ1: How does the concept of manufacturing as a service support or enable changeability? And RQ2: How does the concept of changeability support manufacturing as a service? To answer the two questions, this paper provides a theoretical analysis of the interrelation between Manufacturing as a Service and Changeability. As future steps in the project, the focus will be on developing a framework to assess the interchangeable support of MaaS and changeability and furthermore validating it through real industrial cases provided by partners in the MAASive project, the Horizon Europe Project which provides partial funding to the present study.

Figure 1. Bidirectional support of MaaS and Changeability

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REFERENCES

- Adamson, G., Wang, L., Holm, M., & Moore, P. (2017). Cloud manufacturing – a critical review of recent development and future trends. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 30, 347–380.
- Albinsson, P. A., & Yasanthi Perera, B. (2012). Alternative marketplaces in the 21st century: Building community through sharing events. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 11(4), 303–315.
- Bulut, S., Wende, M., Wagner, C., & Anderl, R. (2021). Impact of Manufacturing-as-a-Service: Business Model Adaption for Enterprises. *Procedia CIRP*, 104, 1286–1291.
- Chaudhuri, A., Datta, P. P., Fernandes, K. J., & Xiong, Y. (2021). Optimal pricing strategies for manufacturing-as-a service platforms to ensure business sustainability. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 234, 108065.

- Corti, D., Bettoni, A., Montini, E., Barni, A., & Arica, E. (2021). Empirical evidence from the design of a MaaS platform. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 54(1), 73–79.
- ElMaraghy, H. A., & Wiendahl, H.-P. (2009). Changeability – An Introduction. In H. A. ElMaraghy (Ed.), *Changeable and Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems* (pp. 3–24). Springer.
- ElMaraghy, H., & Wiendahl, H.-P. (2016). Changeable Manufacturing. *CIRP Encyclopedia of Production Engineering*, 1–7.
- Gawer, A., & Cusumano, M. A. (2013). Industry Platforms and Ecosystem Innovation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 31(3), 417–433.
- Goldhar, J. D., & Jelinek, M. (1990a). Manufacturing as a service business: CIM in the 21st century. *Computers in Industry*, 14(1), 225–245.
- Goldhar, J. D., & Jelinek, M. (1990b). Manufacturing as a service business: CIM in the 21st century. *Computers in Industry*, 14(1–3), 225–245.
- Gong, X., Wang, S., Jiao, R. J., & Gebraeel, N. Z. (2023). Collaborative contracting for Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) by information content measurement and decision tree learning. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 56, 101911.
- Hasan, M. A., Shankar, R., & Sarkis, J. (2007). A study of barriers to agile manufacturing. *International Journal of Agile Systems and Management*, 2(1), 1.
- Hunka, A. D., Linder, M., & Habibi, S. (2020). Determinants of consumer demand for circular economy products. A case for reuse and remanufacturing for sustainable development. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(1), 535–550.
- Jafarnejad Ghomi, E., Masoud Rahmani, A., & Nasih Qader, N. (2019). Service load balancing, task scheduling and transportation optimisation in cloud manufacturing by applying queuing system. *Enterprise Information Systems*, 13, 865–894.
- Koren, Y. (2019). The Emergence of Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems (RMSs). *Springer Series in Advanced Manufacturing*, 1–9.
- Kusiak, A. (2020). Service manufacturing = Process-as-a-Service + Manufacturing Operations-as-a-Service. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 31(1), 1–2.
- Mikusz, M., Heber, D., Katzfuß, C., Monauni, M., & Tauterat, T. (2016). Changeable Manufacturing on the Network Level. *Procedia CIRP*, 41, 27–32.
- Miragliotta, G., Tedaldi, G., & Gastaldi, L. (2022). *A strategic outlook on Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) Platforms: Differences and inspi-rations from traditional platforms ecosystems*.
- Tedaldi, G., & Miragliotta, G. (2021). *Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS): State-of-the-art of up and running solutions and a framework to assess the level of development of a Cloud Manufacturing platform*. ITA.
- Tedaldi, G., & Miragliotta, G. (2023). Early adopters of Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS): State-of-the-art and deployment models. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 34(4), 580–600.
- Wiendahl, H.-P., ElMaraghy, H. A., Nyhuis, P., Zäh, M. F., Wiendahl, H.-H., Duffie, N., & Brieke, M. (2007). Changeable Manufacturing—Classification, Design and Operation. *CIRP Annals*, 56(2), 783–809.
- Zolnowski, A., Weiss, C., & Bohmann, T. (2014). *Representing Service Business Models with the Service Business Model Canvas—The Case of a Mobile Payment Service in the Retail Industry*. 718–727.